

INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR MODELING AND RESEARCH OF PSEUDORANDOM SEQUENCES OF CET-OPERATIONS FOR POST QUANTUM STREAM ENCRYPTION SYSTEMS

V. Rudnytskyi, N. Lada, V. Larin, V. Tkachenko, T. Korotkyi, D. Pidlasyi and D. Tarasenko

Abstract *The task of this research is to identify ways to improve the hierarchically structured IT system model suitable for modeling and researching the symmetrical and non-symmetrical CET-operations. The improvement is based on identifying dependencies between synthesis models of symmetrical/non-symmetrical operations and hierarchy levels. We have defined and fulfilled several objectives to achieve the task mentioned above. We studied the previously mentioned hierarchically structured IT system suitable for modeling and researching the symmetrical CET-operations as our first objective. We have then defined the new correlations between the hierarchy levels as a part of expanding the capabilities of the system mentioned previously. This knowledge allowed us to improve this system by implementing an additional hierarchy level and restructuring and improving the correlations within the system. In addition, we have proven the necessity of using general databases and the knowledge base for unification of software implementation of IT system. The new approach simplifies any further improvements of the IT system and allows adapting it to different tasks related to synthesis and research of CET-operations. Direct and inverse single-operand CET-operations are synthesized and analyzed on the first hierarchy level. Based on the defined attributes of single-operand CET-operations, two-operand CET-operation is synthesized on the second hierarchy level. The third hierarchy level is necessary for synthesis of a group of two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation based on the chosen two-operand CET-operation. Afterward, the acquired group of two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation is used to generate the pseudorandom sequences of two-operand CET-operations on the fourth hierarchy level. The ability to define objectives for both single- and two-operand CET-operations allows controlling the attributes of the newly generated pseudorandom sequences of CET-operations. Our previous suggestion regarding the databases revolves around our proposition to store all the synthesized CET-operations, their synthesis parameters and attributes in these databases. We also recommend storing the implementation models of synthesis methods in the knowledge base, for instance, models used for creating CET-operations and their groups, as well as models used for generation of pseudorandom sequences of CET-operations. Usage of both the database and knowledge base will allow to quickly restructure the system, thus adapting it to the different research tasks related to creation of limited resources post-quantum information protection systems.*

Keywords: Information systems, limited resource cryptography, stream encryption, CET-encryption, CET-operations, two-operand operations

1. Introduction

Current demands for improving the protection of data, which is stored, processed and transmitted by the information protection computer systems and networks, revolve around the simultaneous decrease in the number of utilized devices and increase in their functionality [1]. The amount of data required for the real-time transmission, processing, and storage grows exponentially. However, reduction in size or energy capacity decreases hardware and software resources used in the processes mentioned prior. Thus, developing a proper course of actions related to protecting information with limited resource devices grows ever more important [2-3]. The primary competitive advantages of any kind of information technology from personal and to the state level (for example public administration) revolve around privacy and application of the most effective and modern methods [4-7].

Cryptographic security remains among the most effective solutions for the issue mentioned above [8-9]. Yet fully ensuring the competitive advantages mentioned previously is a very demanding process. The majority of cryptographic algorithms lose their effectiveness or become very difficult to apply due to hardware and software limitations. This is the main reason why limited resource (low resource) [10] or lightweight [11-13] cryptography has become an increasingly popular method. The majority of related studies are dedicated to improving the qualitative variables of physical and cryptographic security [14], evaluation of lightweight cryptography for embedded systems [15], modification of schemes used in lightweight cryptography [16], comparative analysis of light cryptographic algorithms [17-18], etc. However, we consider the issue of increasing the quality of such low resource systems of stream encryption underresearched.

2. Analysis of sources and target setting

CET-transformation of data is a prominent development branch that offers a great opportunity for improvement of the limited resource cryptography. CET-operations are fundamental for CET-transformation of data since they ensure transformation of the incoming data C_i -quanta in a cryptogram [19]. CET-operation itself is an operation of cryptographic encoding (Cryptographic Encoding Theory – CET). Every CET-operation represents a set of elementary functions. Depending on the incoming data C_i -quanta, each elementary function creates a corresponding outgoing data C_i -quantum, for example, the first function creates the first C_i -quantum, the second function — the second, etc. [19]. In the field of Ukrainian cryptography, the term “CET-operation” for defining the operations used for cryptographic coding has been adopted primarily to increase the clarity of the corresponding English articles related to cryptography. This measure allowed avoiding tautology during translation. A CET-operation can also be defined as a mathematical model of one or several substitution tables, while the previously

mentioned elementary functions can be defined as the implementation models for digits in these substitution tables. The number of substitution tables and correlations between them define the type of CET-operation, which can be either a single-operand, two-operand, or multi-operand [19]. A single-operand CET-operation operates with one substitution table. A cipher based on one single-operand CET-operation can be defined as a cipher of forward substitution [20]. However, if the number of Ci-quanta of CET-operation is not identical to the number of bits used for character representation of a message, then a cipher implements a substitution while ensuring the aliasing of symbols. A stream cipher that operates with several single-operand CET-operations is defined as a monotonic substitution cipher or polyalphabetic cipher. [20]. Usually, the number of bits used for transformation is not identical to the number of bits used for symbol encoding. Therefore, the ciphers mentioned previously can be defined as the modified ciphers of polygraphic substitution capable of ensuring the aliasing of symbols [19]. Single-operand CET-operations with different numbers of data Ci-quanta are usable for creating the ciphers with the fluctuating size of transformation unit [19].

There are numerous articles dedicated to cryptographic coding and CET-encryption. We can distinguish several categories among their vast numbers. The first category of paper describes the methods of synthesis and analysis of single-operand operations, as well as their application [21-22]. The second category deals with the same scientific issues concerning two-operand operations [23-24]. The acquired scientific results are based on computer modeling. This method is very effective since it allows to search and identify the incoming data to ensure the research flow. This is the reason why numerous papers, such as [25-27], are dedicated to developing information technologies suitable for modeling and researching CET-operations. We will now analyze the papers mentioned above in detail.

The authors of [25] have described the first information system for building and researching logical functions and single-operand operations. At first, this information system consisted of just two components: an encoding/decoding unit and a logic-state analyzer. Later its functionality was expanded by introducing a proper GUI and a function to save the acquired formalized models. These new changes contributed greatly towards ensuring the simplicity and effectiveness of modeling of single-operand CET-operations. Having created a base of the synthesized models of single-operand CET-operations, the authors have further expanded the system by adding a function for modeling groups of elementary functions, as well as an option for conducting the statistical analysis [26]. However, the further development of CET-encryption resulted in a gradual transition from single-operand CET-operations to multi-operand. Today it is impossible to expand the modeling-related capabilities of such systems and conduct further research of CET-operations without introducing improvements in the realm of computer modeling.

The first mathematical models of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations and their groups became the foundation for the hierarchical information technology

for modeling and research of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations allowing the permutation of operands [27].

All operations generated by the corresponding information system are applicable during creation of block and stream ciphers. However, these types of operations are but a small part of the entirety of two-operand CET-operations as a whole. Finally, there are no means of automation available for use during creation of stream encryption systems as a part of research related to non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations.

3. Purpose and objectives of research

Purpose of the article. The purpose is the development of the model of a hierarchically structured IT system suitable for modeling and researching the symmetrical and non-symmetrical CET-operations. The model is based on the identification of dependencies between synthesis models of symmetrical/non-symmetrical operations and hierarchy level. Addressing the issue mentioned above is crucial for expanding the connection between the models of hierarchical levels of information system. We have established the following objectives to fulfill the aforementioned purpose:

- to study the model of hierarchically structured IT system suitable for modeling and researching the symmetrical CET-operations;
- to study new connections between the hierarchy levels to ensure smooth and unhindered modeling and research of non-symmetrical CET-operations;
- to improve the model of hierarchically structured IT system by implementing an additional hierarchy level, as well as restructuring and improving the correlations within the system;
- to prove the necessity of using general databases and the knowledge base for unification of software implementation of IT systems;
- to lay the foundation for further improvement of the corresponding IT system and its adaptation to new tasks related to synthesis and research of CET-operations.

4. Materials and methods

A CET-operation can be defined as a mathematical model of a substitution table. A single-operand CET-operation is a tuple of elementary functions. Each of these elementary functions implements a model of the corresponding column from a substitution table. According to [19], a model of single-operand nCi-quanta CET-operation can be illustrated in the following way:

$$C(x) = C(f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x), \dots, f_n(x)), \text{ or } C \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \dots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \\ f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \\ \dots \\ f_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are the incoming data Ci-quanta; $f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \dots, f_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ are elementary functions used for implementation of the corresponding outgoing data Ci-quanta.

If $C(C(x)) = x$ is valid, then a single-operand CET-operation is symmetrical. If $C(C(x)) \neq x$ is valid, then a single-operand CET-operation is non-symmetrical. The expression $C'(C(x)) = x$ is valid for all non-symmetrical CET-operations [19]. The number of paired permutations of tuple elements is lower than the number of nonpaired permutations. Therefore, the number of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations is lower than the number of non-symmetrical single-operand CET-operations.

Two-operand CET-operations are based on the single-operand CET-operations and represent an implementation model of a tuple of single-operand CET-operations. A model of a two-operand CET-operation can be illustrated in the following way:

$$C(x, y) = C(C_1(x), C_2(x), C_3(x), \dots, C_k(x)), \tag{2}$$

where k is a number of single-operand operations in a tuple of a two-operand CET-operation.

If $k = 2^m$, then a two-operand CET-operation (1) can be illustrated in the following way:

$$C(x, y) = \begin{cases} C_1(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; \dots; y_m = 0 \\ C_2(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 0; y_2 = 0; \dots; y_m = 1 \\ \dots\dots\dots & \dots\dots\dots \\ C_k(x), & \text{if } y_1 = 1; y_2 = 1; \dots; y_m = 1 \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

A two-operand CET-operation can also be defined as an implementation model of a two-dimensional substitution table.

We would like to point out the fact that a number of tuple elements of single-operand operations in a two-operand operation may not always be identical to the number of tuple elements of elementary functions in a single-operand CET-operation. The same principle applies to the number of elementary functions in tuples of single-operand operations serving as the foundation for a two-operand operation.

Models (1) and (3) allow formally categorizing two-operand CET-operations.

If $C(C(x, y), y) = x$ is valid, then a two-operand CET-operation is symmetrical. If $C(C(x, y), y) \neq x$ is valid, then a two-operand CET-operation is non-symmetrical. The expression $C'(C(x, y), y) = x$ is valid for all non-symmetrical CET-operations. We can thus conclude the following:

- A two-operand CET-operation is symmetrical if it consists of symmetrical single-operand CET-operations.
- A two-operand CET-operation is non-symmetrical if at least one single-operand operation from which it consists of is non-symmetrical.

- Symmetry of a two-operand CET-operation is defined solely based on the symmetry or lack thereof of the single-operand operations from which it consists. It has no dependency on the number of data Ci-quanta transformed by each single-operand operation.

We will now analyze permutation of operands. We acquire the following results upon permutation of operands in a two-operand CET-operation (3):

$$C(y, x) = \begin{cases} C_1(y), & \text{if } x_1 = 0; x_2 = 0; \dots; x_m = 0 \\ C_2(y), & \text{if } x_1 = 0; x_2 = 0; \dots; x_m = 1 \\ \dots\dots\dots & \dots\dots\dots \\ C_k(y), & \text{if } x_1 = 1; x_2 = 1; \dots; x_m = 1 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

CET-operation $C(x, y)$ has an inverse operation $C'(x, y)$, whereas:

$$C'(C(x, y), y) = x. \quad (5)$$

We acquire the following results upon permutation of operands in both the direct and inverse CET-operations:

$$C'(C(y, x), x) = y. \quad (6)$$

If model (5) is valid, then model (6) is automatically considered valid as well. If $x \neq y$ is valid, then:

$$\begin{cases} C'(C(x, y), y) \neq C'(C(y, x), x) \\ C(x, y) \neq C(y, x) \\ C'(x, y) \neq C'(y, x) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

By analyzing (7), we can conclude that permutation of operands usually results in an acquisition of a different result of implementing a CET-operation. This principle is most often traceable in operations of inverse transformation of data before and after permutation of operands.

The exceptions from the rule mentioned above are symmetrical two-operand CET-operations that allow permutation of operands. The following expressions are valid for these operations:

$$\begin{cases} C(x, y) = C(y, x) \\ C'(x, y) = C'(y, x) \\ C'(C(x, y), y) = C'(C(y, x), x) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The previously described hierarchical information technology for modeling and research of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations that allow permutation of operands was analyzed specifically to highlight the operations, which correspond with (8) [26].

The information system mentioned above has three hierarchical levels. The first hierarchical level is used to analyze and synthesize single-operand CET-operations. The second hierarchical level is used to analyze and synthesize two-operand CET-operations based on the previously synthesized single-operand CET-operations. The third hierarchical level is used to analyze and synthesize pseudorandom sequences of two-operand CET-operations based on the previously synthesized single- and two-operand CET-operations.

5. Analysis of the results

We have established a possibility to create groups of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations that allow permutation of operands to an accuracy of permutation of the results. This allows conducting an additional transformation of the implementation results of a two-operand CET-operation by a single-operand operation during synthesis of two-operand CET-operations or groups of CET-operations.

We can illustrate the synthesis of two-operand CET-operations within a corresponding system in the following way:

$$C_i(x, y) = C_i(C(x, y)), \quad (9)$$

where i is an element of a set of single-operand CET-operations used to synthesize two-operand CET-operations. Only those single-operand CET-operations, which correspond with the specified synthesis conditions, are included in this set.

Direct and inverse operations with both permuted and not permuted operands are identical in symmetrical two-operand CET-operations according to (8).

According to the attributes of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations and attributes of (8), direct and inverse CET-operations are identical before and after the permutation of operands. Thus, a corresponding system operates only with the direct CET-operations.

We can illustrate the generation process of a pseudorandom sequence of two-operand CET-operations within a corresponding system in the following way:

$$C_{ji}(x, y) = C_j(C_i(C(x, y))), \quad (10)$$

where i is an element of a set of single-operand CET-operations used to synthesize two-operand CET-operations; j is an element of a set of single-operand CET-operations used to generate a pseudorandom sequence of two-operand CET-operations. Sets of single-operand CET-operations used to generate a pseudorandom sequence of two-operand operations and synthesis of this type of operations are usually not identical. Their lack of identical structure exists due to differences in synthesis conditions.

We have established that a hierarchical approach to creating an information system for modeling and research of CET-operations is universal. However, using the analyzed three levels of this hierarchy is enough only during creation and research of one of the groups of CET-operations. Creation of two-operand CET-operations from one classified group relies on operating with identical synthesis models. Expanding the capabilities of the system requires an increase in number of the classified groups of synthesized CET-operations. This expansion increases the number of models used on every hierarchical level and results in application of additional models for creating two-operand CET-operations based on single-operand operations. Thus, we suggest introducing an additional level between the levels of synthesizing the single-operand CET-operations and synthesizing the groups of two-operand CET-operations, specifically the level of synthesizing the two-operand CET-operations.

Model of hierarchical information system for creation and research of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which allow permutation of operands, is illustrated on Picture 1. The model takes into account expressions (9) and (10).

Picture 1. Model of hierarchical information system for creation and research of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which allow permutation of operands.

We will now analyze the attributes of the hierarchical systems with four levels. These systems fulfill the same purpose of creating and researching symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which allow or do not allow permutation of operands.

The first hierarchical level is used to analyze and synthesize single-operand CET-operations.

Synthesis of two-operand operation proceeds on the second hierarchical level based on the symmetrical single-operand CET-operations ($C(x) = C'(x)$). Synthesis of symmetrical two-operand operations that allow permutation of operands is possible only under the following condition: $C(x, y) = C(y, x)$. $C(y, x)$ may not exist for other symmetrical two-operand operations. In addition, the following expression may apply: $C(x, y) \neq C(y, x)$.

Synthesis of a group of two-operand operations, which allow permutation of operands, proceeds on the third hierarchical level to an accuracy of permutation of the result (9).

If there is no option for permutating the operands, then there is no limitation for commutative attributes of a CET-operation $C(x, y) \neq C(y, x)$.

Because $C_i(C(x)) \neq C_i(C(y))$, and $C_i(C(x)) = C_j(x)$, where $C_j(C_j(x)) \neq x$, then the following expression is valid:

$$C_i(C(x, y)) \neq C'_i(C(x, y)). \tag{11}$$

Model (11) shows, that synthesis of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which does not allow permutation of operands, to an accuracy of the permutation of the results modifies single-operand CET-operations. Modification may alter these single-operand CET-operations. They can either remain symmetrical or become non-symmetrical.

Permutation of the second operand alters only the sequence of single-operand operations in a tuple without modifying the operations themselves. Thus, we suggest applying this permutation during creation of a group of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation:

$$C_i(x, y) = C(x, C_i(y)). \quad (12)$$

The fourth hierarchical level exists to generate the pseudorandom sequence of operations according to model (10). Should there be a necessity to generate the same sequence for symmetrical operations without the need to permute the operands, then we suggest transforming the second operand to an accuracy of permutation:

$$C_{ji}(x, y) = C(x, C_j(C_i(y))). \quad (13)$$

The validity of model (13) is based on the validity of model (12).

Synthesis and research of symmetrical two-operand CET-operations that allow permutation of operands can be automated. Doing so requires a replacement of several models within a hierarchical system (Picture 1). Model (9) should be replaced by model (12) on the third level, while model (10) should be replaced by model (13) on the fourth level. The models (9) and (12), as well as (10) and (13) can be combined. Performing this action provides an option to create and research all symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which allow or do not allow permutation of operands.

Defining the connection between direct and inverse operations is a requirement for synthesis and research of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations.

We will now analyze the attributes of a model of a hierarchical information system for creation and research of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations. The correlation between direct and inverse operations is a mandatory requirement to ensure application of two-operand CET-operations. Therefore, it is necessary to create a set of direct and a set of inverse CET-operations on the first hierarchical level. A tuple of direct single-operand CET-operations is a requirement for the proper creation of a direct two-operand CET-operation on the second hierarchical level. The user can create an inverse non-symmetrical two-operand operation by substituting the direct single-operand CET-operations by inverse operations within the created tuple.

Single-operand CET-operations themselves are unaffected by the modification of the second operand. Only their sequence in a tuple is affected. Modification of the second operand in an inverse two-operand CET-operation enables creation of a tuple of inverse single-operand operations, thus allowing creation of an inverse two-operand operation. We can thus describe the creation process of a group of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the second operand on the third hierarchical level by the following models:

$$\begin{aligned} C_i(x, y) &= C(x, C_i(y)) \\ C'_i(x, y) &= C'(x, C_i(y)) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $C'_i(x, C_i(y)) = x$.

A pseudorandom sequence of CET-operations can also be generated to an accuracy of permutation of the second operand:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ji}(x, y) &= C(x, C_j(C_i(y))) \\ C'_{ji}(x, y) &= C'(x, C_j(C_i(y))) \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where $C'_{ji}(x, C_j(C_i(y))) = x$.

Model of a hierarchical information system for creation and research of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which implements models (14) and (15), is illustrated in Picture 2.

Picture 2. Model of hierarchical information system for creation and research of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations to an accuracy of permutation of the second operand.

Models of hierarchical information systems illustrated in Picture 1 and Picture 2 differ in their attributes regarding creation of operation groups and generation of pseudorandom sequences. This fact justifies utilization of databases and knowledge bases during software implementation of these systems.

6. Results analysis

Database is a reliable tool for storing all the synthesized CET-operations including the data regarding their attributes and synthesis parameters. A knowledge base is well suited for storing implementation models of synthesis methods, models used for creating groups of operations, as well as models used for generation of pseudorandom sequences of CET-operations. Application of a database and a knowledge base provides an option for rapid system adaptation for solving different tasks and improving the system itself by expanding both the database and knowledge base.

The limitations regarding the application of the described hierarchical system exist regardless of capacity of computing devices. They are primarily connected with an increase in the number of CET-operations that occurs when the number of data Ci-quanta increases. The number of single-operand nCi-quanta CET-operations is defined as $2^n!$ [19]. The number of two-operand nCi-quanta CET-operations is defined as $C_{2^n}^k = \frac{2^n!}{k!(2^n!-k)!}$ if these operations are created based on tuples of k single-operand CET-operations. A group of the modified operations to an accuracy of permutation is then synthesized based on every synthesized two-operand CET-operation. Number of the modified operations within a group is defined as $k!$. Under condition $k = 2^m$, a group of operations can be created based on a group of single-operand nCi-quanta CET-operations.

Application of a database and a knowledge base in a hierarchical system partially decreases the consequences of an increase in the number of operations and greatly expands the available options for researching the processes of practical synthesis of pseudorandom sequences of CET-operations.

7. Conclusions

During our research, we have developed a model of a hierarchical system for modeling and research of both symmetrical and non-symmetrical CET-operations with an additional hierarchical level. Our improvement is based on the previous model, and is necessary due to the demand to synthesize CET-operations with new attributes. We created the new model by defining the dependencies between synthesis models of symmetrical and non-symmetrical operations. The defined dependencies expand the correlations between models of hierarchical levels of information system.

The discovery mentioned above justifies our suggestion to use databases and knowledge bases during software implementation of these systems. A database is an effective tool for storing synthesis-related data, as well as synthesized operations and their attributes. Models used for synthesis of operations, groups of operations, as well as models for generation of pseudorandom sequences of CET-operations can be stored in knowledge bases. We suggest usage of databases and knowledge bases to lay the foundation for further improvement of the corresponding IT system and its adaptation to new tasks related to synthesis and research of CET-operations.

In conclusion, we also suggest directing future research to define the methods applicable for creation of non-symmetrical two-operand CET-operations, which allow permutation of operands, studying groups of these operations, and defining the rules related to generation of their pseudorandom sequences. The analyzed information system can be applied in further research and development of low resource post quantum systems for data protection.

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Volodymyr RUDNYTSKYI - Professor, Doctor of Technical Sciences, Chief Researcher, *Corresponding author*
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Nataliia LADA - Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Leading Researcher
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Volodymyr LARIN - Associate Professor, Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Head of Department
State Scientific Research Institute of Armament and Military Equipment Testing and Certification, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Viktor TKACHENKO - Professor, Doctor of Military Sciences, Professor
Air Force Science Center, Ivan Kozhedub Kharkiv National Air Force University, Kharkiv, Ukraine

Tymofii KOROTKYI - Postgraduate Student
Cherkasy State Technological University, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Dmytro PIDLASYI - Assistant
Cherkasy State Technological University, Cherkasy, Ukraine

Denys TARASENKO - Candidate of Technical Sciences (PhD in Technology and Engineering), Doctoral Student
Cherkasy State Technological University, Cherkasy, Ukraine